

Minerals And Amino Acids Profile Of Bee Pollen From A Selected Apiary In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Bee pollen is an indispensable apicultural product in many diets due to its high nutritional and medicinal value. The research investigated its minerals and amino acids content using standard methods of analyses. The results revealed that Potassium is the most abundant macro element in the fruit ($360.56 \pm 4.92\text{mg}$), followed by calcium ($245.69 \pm 3.12\text{mg}$), phosphorus ($197.76 \pm 1.87\text{mg}$), magnesium ($98.46 \pm 1.08\text{mg}$), and sodium ($27.63 \pm 2.51\text{mg}$). On the other hand, iron is the most abundant micro element ($14.44 \pm 1.75\text{mg}$), followed by manganese ($6.97 \pm 0.77\text{mg}$), zinc ($4.33 \pm 0.98\text{mg}$), copper ($3.50 \pm 0.12\text{mg}$), and nickel ($2.51 \pm 0.09\text{mg}$). Of the essential amino acids, leucine, lysine and aromatic (phenylalanine and tyrosine) are the predominant acids, while glutamic, aspartic and alanine were found to be the major non-essential amino acids. The essential amino acids were above the recommended level by Food and Agricultural Organization/World Health Organization (FAO/WHO) for both adults and pre-school children aged 2-5 years. The present investigation indicates the potential use of bee pollen as rich source of many important nutrients that appear to have a very positive effect on human health.

Keywords: Bee Pollen; Minerals, Amino Acids, Essential; Non- Essential

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, bee pollen has been attaining importance as an indispensable apicultural product in human diet due to its high nutritional, functional, and medicinal value [1]. The nutritional contents vary according to the botanical source, geographic origin, beekeeping activities, collection time and environmental conditions [2]. In addition to presence of carbohydrate, protein and fiber, bee pollen is also rich in essential fatty acids, minerals and vitamins together with polyphenols (mainly flavonoids), carotenoids and phytosterols, which signify the role of bee pollen as a natural diet supplement [3]. It has been used in traditional medicine for centuries and recent studies exhibited its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-mutagenic antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory and ant cancerous activities [4].

Pollen is a valuable food source for bees and bee larvae and is the product of the male reproductive cells of flowering plants [5]. Bee pollen (Plate 1) is a raw material from which bees produce bee bread. They collect pollen from plant anthers, mix it with a small dose of the secretion from salivary glands or

nectar, and place it in specific baskets (*Corbiculae*) which are situated on the tibia of their hind legs. These are called pollen loads [6]. In the hive, the collected pollen, dampened with saliva and fragmented by flightless bees, is packed in honeycomb cells, the surface of the collected pollen is covered with a thin layer of honey and wax. The substance which has been created is bee bread which undergoes anaerobic fermentation and is preserved thanks to the arising lactic acid. Bee bread constitutes the basic protein source for the bee colony. It is also the source of nutritional and mineral substances for royal jelly produced by worker bees [6]. It is an important bee product with high nutritional value and a potential source of natural antioxidants which have a positive effect on human health, and is therefore regarded as "functional foods". The product is rich in proteins, simple sugars, essential amino acids and fatty acids. These features strengthen immunity and help the body to fight bacteria, which will keep the body healthy, provided the body can perform a quality tissue repair [7]. Additionally, bee pollen presents an excellent source of antioxidant vitamins such as vitamins A, C, and E [8].

(a)

Plate 1 (a); (b): Bee pollen [9]

(b)

Various investigations on the chemical compositions and advantages of bee pollen were conducted in many countries around the globe and thus establishing quality guidelines of bee pollen for its use as food [10]. The present study investigated the minerals and amino acids composition of bee pollen obtained from an apiary of modern bee hives in Sokoto State, Nigeria, as there is no available literature on its nutritional quality from this part of the country which could be as a result of in availability of modern bee keeping equipment, and lack of proper knowledge of the various bee products apart from the bee honey. The research study is aimed to evaluate the minerals and amino acids composition of bee pollen so as to provide clear understanding on its potential use as a source of nutrients supplement and in the formulation of some fortified animal feeds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and Chemicals

All the reagents and chemicals used in the research such as HCl, NaOH, H₂SO₄ etc were of analytical grade obtained from the local suppliers and were made by Sigma Chemical Co., Aldrich Chemicals Co., U.S.A. High-quality distilled water obtained using a Milli-Q system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA), was used exclusively.

Sample Collection and Treatment

The study material was collected in February, 2021 from an apiary containing modern bee hives located at More, Kware Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria. Twelve (12) Hives were chosen randomly and from each of the hives combs containing pollen were carefully selected, they were then air dried for 8 hr to facilitate sorting for removing the pollen. The pollen was carefully removed from the comb, packed in a plastic container and transported to the laboratory where it was stored in a refrigerator until analyses.

Mineral Analysis

Eleven elements were determined using microwave plasma-atomic emission spectroscopy (MP-AES) with slight modifications [26]. An Agilent 4100 MP-

AES (Agilent Technologies) equipped with an Agilent SPS 3 Auto Sampler and Agilent 4107 Nitrogen Generator was used for analysis, where the sample introduction system comprised a single pass glass cyclonic spray chamber, glass concentric nebulizer, orange-green for sample tubing and blue-blue for waste tubing. Other instrument conditions were 172 kPa nebulizer pressure, 3 s read time and 15 s stabilization time. All the required calibration standards were prepared using 5% HNO₃. Each sample was digested with 10 mL of concentrated HNO₃, 6.5 mL of concentrated HCl and 1 mL of H₂O₂ for 7 h at 180 °C and, after cooling, it was diluted to make the final volume of 50 ml [11].

Amino Acids Analysis

Duplicate samples were hydrolyzed by transferring 50mg of the sample into a 15mL ampoule, adding 5mL of 6M HCl, sealing the vial under vacuum, flushed with nitrogen, and digesting at 110°C for 24 h. The Sulphur containing amino acids were determined using performic acid. Amino acids analyses were performed by high performance liquid chromatography (Shimadzu, G-C-14A, Kyoto, Japan) [11].

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were statistically analyzed using One way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with SPSS version 16.0 statistical package and the results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of three replicates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The results of minerals and amino acids content of bee pollen are presented in Table 1 and 2 respectively, while that of the amino acids score is presented in Table 3. Potassium recorded the highest value with 360.56 ± 4.92 mg/100g, while copper was the lowest with 1.98 ± 0.21 mg/100g dry weight. Leucine is the most abundant essential amino acids 13.24 g/100g protein, and cysteine recorded the lowest value of 2.73 g/100g protein.

Table 1: Minerals composition of bee pollen on dry weight basis (mg/100g)

Mineral elements	Concentration (mg/ 100g)
Na	27.63 \pm 2.51
K	360.56 \pm 4.92
P	197.76 \pm 1.87
Ca	245.69 \pm 3.12
Mg	98.46 \pm 1.08
Mn	6.97 \pm 0.77
Fe	14.44 \pm 1.75
Co	3.50 \pm 0.12
Cu	1.98 \pm 0.21
Ni	2.51 \pm 0.09
Zn	4.33 \pm 0.98

Table 2: Amino acids profile of the bee pollen (g/100g protein)

Amino Acid	Concentration
Lysine*	7.11
Histidine	5.82
Arginine	3.75
Aspartic acid	8.60
Threonine*	6.19
Serine	4.02
Glutamic acid	9.68
Proline	5.34
Glycine	3.06
Alanine	6.40
Cysteine*	2.73
Valine*	5.37
Methionine*	4.09
Isoleucine*	5.35
Leucine*	13.24
Tyrosine*	4.25
Phenylalanine*	3.72

The data are mean value of duplicate results.

* Essential amino acids.

Table 3: Amino acids score of bee pollen

EAA	Concentration (g/100g protein)	WHO Ideal protein		[(%Amino acid)/ideal]x100	
		A	B	Children	Adult
Isoleucine	5.35	2.8	1.3	191	411.53
Leucine	13.24	6.6	1.9	125	434
Lysine	7.11	5.8	1.6	122	444
Total sulphur EAAs	6.82	2.5	1.7	272	401
Total aromatic EAAs	7.97	6.3	1.9	126	419
Threonine	6.19	3.4	0.9	182	687
Valine	5.37	3.5	1.3	153	413
Histidine*	5.82	1.9	1.6	306	362
Total EAAs	57.87				
Total non-EAAs	40.85				
Total amino acids	98.72				
%EAAs in total amino acids	58.62				
%non-EAAs in total amino acids	41.37				

*essential for children

A = WHO/FAO/UNU ideal protein for preschool children aged 2-5years. (FAO/UN, 2013)

B = WHO/FAO/UNU ideal protein for adult (FAO/UN, 2013). EAAs = Essential amino acids.

DISCUSSION

Minerals Composition

The minerals profile of the fruit was reported in mg/100g on dry weight basis and the result is presented in Table 1. Potassium was the most abundant macro element in the pollen 360.56 ± 4.92 mg), followed by calcium (245.69 ± 3.12 mg), phosphorus (197.76 ± 1.87 mg), magnesium (98.46 ± 1.08 mg), and sodium (27.63 ± 2.51 mg). On the other hand, iron was the most abundant micro element (14.44 ± 1.75 mg), followed by manganese (6.97 ± 0.77 mg), zinc (4.33 ± 0.98 mg), copper (3.50 ± 0.12 mg), and nickel (2.51 ± 0.09 mg). The result obtained was in agreement with that reported by Manta Thakur – Vikas-Nande [10] and Admassu *et al.* [12] for pollen obtained from Northwestern and Southwestern regions of India and that obtained from Southwestern Ethiopia respectively, which indicated the potential use of pollen as a supplement of both macro and micro mineral elements which are important for general body functioning. For example sodium and potassium are important component of

body electrolytes. Potassium helps to maintain body weight and regulate water and acid base balance in the blood and tissues [13]. Calcium and phosphorus are associated with each other for growth and maintenance of bones, teeth, and muscles [14]. Iron is vital in the formation of the central nervous system and is an essential trace element for haemoglobin formation, normal functioning of the central nervous system and in the oxidation of carbohydrates, proteins, and fats [15; 16]. Manganese is believed to support the immune system, regulates blood sugar levels and is involved in the production of energy and cell reproduction. Birth defects can possibly result when an expecting mother does not get enough of manganese [17]. Zinc is an important trace element for protein and nucleic acid synthesis and normal body development [18].

Amino Acids Profile

Table 2 shows the amino acid profile of the bee pollen. Twenty amino acids are commonly found as components of proteins [19]. In this research,

seventeen amino acids were detected as a result of the conversion of glutamine and asparagine to glutamic and aspartic acids respectively [19] and complete destruction of tryptophan during acid hydrolysis [20]. The result indicated that essential amino acids are higher in concentration (58.62%) compared to the non-essential amino acids which constitute 41.37% of the total amino acids analysed. Among the essential amino acids, leucine, lysine and aromatic (phenylalanine and tyrosine) are the predominant acids, while glutamic, aspartic and alanine were found to be the major non-essential amino acids and this is in agreement with the finding of Manta Thakur – Vikas-Nande [10] for pollen obtained from North Western and South Western regions of India.

Ideally, the protein in the diet should provide the body's requirement of all the essential amino acids in the same proportions. The contents of essential amino acid in the pollen are compared with the amino acids requirement stated by the WHO for adults and children aged 2 – 5 years [21] and the result presented in Table 3. The result showed that all the essential amino acids exceeded the reference value for both adults and the pre-school children, which further suggests the potentiality of using bee pollen as a “healthy” source of high-quality protein.

CONCLUSION

From the results obtained, bee pollen is a promising source of both macro and micro mineral elements such as Na, K, P, Ca, Mg, Mn, Zn, Co, Ni and Fe. The pollen analyzed is also rich in both essential and non-essential amino acids ready to supply the body requirement of the amino acids. The study therefore, suggests the use of bee pollen if properly utilized as a potential source of food supplement.

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